

ANALYSIS OF PHYSICAL AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF Gd^{3+} DOPPED YOF

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Abstract

The band gap energy and density of the sample were found by analytical method. The density was found to increase up to 7 mol% depicts the compactness of the sample and then decreases with gadolinium content. Molar volume (V_m), Gd^{3+} ion concentration (N), refractive index (n), electronic Polarizability (α_e), reflection loss (R_L), polaron radius(r_p), internuclear distance (r_i), field strength (F) and dielectric constant(ϵ) of the sample were calculated.

Keywords: YOF, Gd^{3+} electronic Polarizability, reflection loss, polaron radius.

1. Introduction

Density and molar volume are fundamental physical properties of a substance. These parameters provide insights into the packing efficiency and structural arrangement of atoms or molecules within a material. Physical properties encompass characteristics such as density, molar volume, Optical properties, on the other hand, describe how a material interacts with light, including parameters like refractive index, reflection loss, transmission coefficient, and optical band gap energy. These properties are often interconnected; for instance, changes in physical structure can influence optical behaviour.

The refractive index is a measure of how much the speed of light is reduced when passing through a material, and it is related to the electronic polarizability. Electronic polarizability describes the ease with which the electron cloud of an atom or molecule can be distorted by an external electric field, such as that of an electromagnetic wave.

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Density and molar volume

The density of the YOF sample was found using Archimedes Principle. Acetone (0.786 g/cm³) was used as an immersion liquid for the sample to measure its density. The sample density was calculated using the relation

$$\rho_{sample} = \frac{W_A}{W_A - W_B} 0.786 \text{ (g/cm}^3\text{)}$$

Where W_A is the weight of sample in air and W_B is the weight of sample in acetone. The measurement was repeated three times for each sample to approximate the average value. The values are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1

The code, compositions of the glasses prepared, boron molar volume (V_m), oxygen packing density (OPD) and boron atomic separation $\langle d_B - d_B \rangle$.

Composition in mol %		V_m	OPD
YOF	Gd ₂ O ₃	(x10 ⁻⁵ m ³)	(g-atom/litre)
99	1	29.080	35.075
97	3	28.932	36.636
95	5	28.601	38.459
93	7	28.691	39.733
91	9	30.063	39.250
89	11	31.829	38.329

Table 1

Phosphor	V_m (x 10 ⁻⁵ m ³)	OPD (g-atom/litre)
YOF:Gd ³⁺ (1 mol%)	29.080	35.075
YOF:Gd ³⁺ (3 mol%)	28.932	36.636
YOF:Gd ³⁺ (5 mol%)	28.601	38.459
YOF:Gd ³⁺ (7 mol%)	28.691	39.733
YOF:Gd ³⁺ (9 mol%)	30.063	39.250
YOF:Gd ³⁺ (11 mol%)	31.829	38.329

The density for the sample increases and the corresponding molar volume decreases up to 7 mol% gadolinium content due to bridging oxygen atoms and then finds opposite nature beyond 7 mol% due to non-bridging oxygen atoms. The non-linear variation of density, molar volume and oxygen packing density (OPD) with Gd^{3+} concentration is due to the electronic and ionic hopping mechanism in the network.

$$OPD = \left(\frac{\rho}{M}\right) * C * 1000$$

Where C is the number of oxygen atoms per formula of composition unit

2.2 Physical and optical properties

Gd^{3+} ion concentration (N), density (ρ) and refractive index (n) were used to estimate the physical and optical properties of the samples such as electronic Polarizability (α_e), reflection loss (R_L), transmission coefficient (T), polaron radius (r_p), internuclear distance (r_i), field strength (F) and dielectric constant (ϵ) using the standard relations and the obtained values are listed in **Table 2**.

Table 2. The physical and optical properties of YOF:Gd³⁺NPs

Physical and optical properties	YOF:Gd ³⁺ Nanophosphors					
	1 mol %	3 mol %	5 mol %	7 mol %	9 mol %	11 mol %
Gd ³⁺ concentration(x 10 ²⁰ ion/cm ³)	2.071	6.2452	10.529	14.695	18.031	20.815
Polaron radius (r_p)(A')	6.81	4.714	3.961	3.544	3.311	3.156
Inter nuclear distance (r_i) (A')	16.902	11.699	9.829	8.796	8.216	7.832
Field Strength(F)(x10 ¹⁶ cm ⁻²)	1.38	2.88	4.078	5.095	5.839	6.426
Refractive Index (n)	2.135	2.154	2.173	2.169	2.171	2.143
Reflection loss R_L	0.1312	0.1340	0.1368	0.1362	0.1365	0.1323
Dielectric constant (ϵ)	4.562	4.642	4.725	4.708	4.716	4.593
Optical dielectric constant (Ppt/dp)	3.562	3.642	3.725	3.708	3.716	3.593
Molar Refraction (R_M) (cm ⁻³)	15.785	15.864	15.842	15.860	16.635	17.347
Metallization criterion	0.457	0.451	0.446	0.447	0.446	0.455
Electronic polarizability(α_m)(A') ³	6.26	6.291	6.282	6.289	6.597	7.597
OPD (g-atom/litre)	35.075	36.636	38.459	39.732	39.25	38.329
Transmission coefficient (T)	0.7608	0.7666	0.7603	0.7630	0.7616	0.7680

2.2.1 Ion concentration (N)

Gadolinium ion concentration (N) can be calculated using the relation[1]

$$N = \frac{(\text{Avogadro's number}) (\text{sample density})}{(\text{sample average molecular weight})} (\% \text{ of RE})$$

The concentration of Gd^{3+} ions increases in the sample with the percentage of Gd^{3+} ions. Because of ratifying the compactness of the system with the addition of gadolinium nitrate, the polaron radius and inter nuclear distance have been calculated using the below relations [2].

$$\text{Polaron radius, } r_p = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \left(\frac{\pi}{6N}\right)^{1/3}$$

$$\text{Inter nuclear distance, } r_i = \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^{1/3}$$

Where N indicates Gd^{3+} ion concentration. **Table 2** depicts a decrease in internuclear distance and polaron radius with Gd^{3+} ion concentration. This result leads to the YOF bond strength increases which enable the strong field near the Gd^{3+} ions. The compactness of the sample shows that the degree of delocalization of electrons decreases, which results in a decrease in band gap energy[3,4].

2.2.2 Field strength (F)

Field strength gives information about the arrangement of ions in the sample, the values were calculated using the relation given below[2]and were presented in **Table 2**.

$$\text{Field strength, } F = \left(\frac{Z}{r_p^2}\right)$$

Where Z is the atomic mass of gadolinium nitrate and r_p is the polaron radius.

The obtained values show the rigidity of the sample increases with Gd^{3+} content. The variation of polaron radius and field strength with gadolinium content is shown in **Fig.1** This figure shows field strength increases while polaron radius decreases. In general field strength and polaron radius shows the opposite behaviour and which is observed in our study.

Fig.1 Variation of filed strength and polaron radius with Gd₂O₃ mol%.

2.2.3 Refractive index and electronic polarizability

When light interacts with atoms of the sample, the parameter refractive index can be calculated and this parameter depends on cation polarizability and density. The electronic polarizability (α_m) is used in the field of applications like optical and electronic devices[8]. Due to the application of the electromagnetic field, the electronic polarizability exhibits distortion in the electronic cloud[9]. The parameter α_m was measured using the Clausius-Mosotti equation

$$\alpha_m = \left(\frac{3}{4\pi N_A}\right) R_m = \frac{R_m}{2.52}$$

Where R_m is the molar refraction and N_A is the Avogadro's number

$$R_m = \left(\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+2}\right) V_m$$

Where V_m is the molar volume and n is the refractive index

The variation of refractive index and electronic polarizability is shown in **Fig.2** From the figure the increasing values may be due to increasing in Gd^{3+} ion content, which has high electronic polarizability ($6.856 \text{ (A}^0\text{)}^3$) than La^{3+} ($4.26 \text{ (A}^0\text{)}^3$)[10,11]. (Search suitable reference for electronic polarizability of Yttrium ion)

Fig.2 Variation of refractive index and electronic polarizability with Gd₂O₃ content.

2.3.4 Reflection loss and transmission coefficient

Reflection loss of investigated sample can be calculated using Fresnel's formula

$$R_L = \left[\frac{n-1}{n+1}\right]^2$$

Where n is the refractive index

The transmission coefficient T can be calculated using the formula

$$T = \frac{2n}{n^2 + 1}$$

The calculated values are listed in Table 2 and are found to be inverse relationship with each other.

2.3.5 Metallization criterion(M)

The metallic and non-metallic nature of the sample was based on metallization criterion values [12].The metallization criterion of the sample can be calculated using the relation given below

$$M = 1 - \frac{R_m}{V_m}$$

Where R_m is molar refraction and V_m molar volume

If the value $R_m/V_m < 1$, sample is non-metallic nature and if the value $R_m/V_m > 1$, sample is metallic nature. It is establishing that from the above equation the sample is non-metallic nature and the calculated values are listed in **Table2**. The highest value of the metallization criterion (0.455) calculated for the Yttrium oxyfluoride disclose that Yttrium -ion reveals the highest band gap energy and insulating nature in the sample, which is confirmed by the band gap energy values. Larger metallization criterion values depict that width of both conduction and valence bands reduces, which intern shows a wider optical band gap energy [13].

2.3.6 Dielectric constant and optical dielectric constant

The dielectric constant of the sample directly depends on its band gap energy and it is calculated using the equation.

$$\varepsilon = n^2$$

Optical dielectric constant can be calculated by using dielectric constant.

$$P \frac{dt}{dp} = \varepsilon - 1$$

Dielectric constant and optical dielectric constant values are shown in Table 2 and are found to increase with gadolinium content.

2.3.7 Optical band gap energy

The optical band gap energy for the sample is calculated using Davis and Mott theory [14]. Optical transitions and electronic band structures were explained because of the absorption effect which could be able to elaborate the optical band gap energy[15]. The absorption coefficient $\alpha(\vartheta)$ is a function of photon energy for indirect and direct band gap energy.

$$\alpha = \alpha_0(h\nu - E_g)^n / h\nu$$

Where E_g optical band gap energy, α_0 is energy independent constant and n is the exponent. If the exponent $n = 1/2$ and 2 represent the allowed direct and indirect transition. The optical band gap energy E_g values were obtained by extrapolating the linear portion of the curve to the X-axis. The obtained values are listed in **Table.1**.

3.Conclusion

The band gap energy and density of the sample were found by analytical method. The density was found to increase up to 7 mol% depicts the compactness of the sample and then decreases with gadolinium content. The YOF bond strength increases which enable the strong field near the Gd^{3+} ions. The compactness of the sample shows that the degree of delocalization of electrons decreases, which results in a decrease in band gap energy. Larger metallization criterion values depict that width of both conduction and valence bands reduces, which intern shows a wider optical band gap energy

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